

FDI IN DIFFERENT SECTORS OF SOUTH ASIAN ECONOMIES

Dr. Namrata Shrivastava

Assistant Professor of Economics, Kalinga University, Raipur(C.G.)

Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to offer a regression model that can be used to explain the distribution of foreign direct investment (FDI) in various industries in South Asian nations. The study's goal is to look at the link between foreign direct investment inflows and the factors that influence them. The research is based on secondary sources. The findings reveal that total GDP is the most important factor influencing FDI influx into South Asian nations. Given the region's large population and expanding developing markets, FDI is pouring in to harness the region's massive and increasing domestic markets. We found that GDP % growth of South Asia in 2019 was \$3,596.91B, increase 4.66% from 2018, GDP per capita South Asia in 2019 was \$1,959, increase 3.44% from 2018, FDI inflows South Asia in 2019 was \$56.69B, increase 16.52% from 2018, Trade openness South Asia in 2018 was 42.31%, increase 2.89% from 2017 and Literacy rate South Asia in 2019 was 72.95%, increase 0.71% from 2018. The multiple regression finding show that FDI and all of its possible factors have a long run equilibrium connection beside only one variable. Trade openness, Per capita income Literacy are the primary factors of FDI in South Asia. In order to attract more FDI, South Asian nations must continue their development momentum, establish policies to make better use of their large labour forces, enhance infrastructure, and implement more open trade policies.

Key words: Foreign direct investment, developing countries, economic goals and economic growth

Introduction

For many nations across the world, foreign direct investment (FDI) is a significant source of external finance. FDI promotes the transfer of technical know-how, management and organisational skills, and access to foreign markets, as well as boosting the productive activities of the host economy, in addition to financial resources. Direct investment is a type of cross-border investment in which a resident of one country (direct investor) has control or a considerable degree of influence over the management of a business (direct investment enterprises) based in a different economy than the direct investor's (OECD, 2008).

Foreign investment, particularly FDI, is frequently seen as a key source of foreign cash, assisting in the alleviation of the balance of payment restriction on economic growth. It also adds to the domestic investment resources needed to boost economic growth. This widely held perspective of foreign investment spurred government to make policy changes in order to attract FDI. In the 1980s and 1990s, China and southeast Asian countries significantly enhanced their economic development by utilising large quantities of FDI. South Asian countries established a restrictive policy framework in the early years of their independence, but have since altered their policies to be more welcoming to international investment in the last two or three decades. Due to the state's prominent position in the development process, import-substituting industrialisation policies were supported in order to achieve self-reliance at such a young age. However, the economies of these countries grew at a slower pace. Following the success of Southeast Asian nations, South

Asian countries implemented market-oriented economic reforms with the goal of integrating their economies with the rest of the globe. South Asian nations have the potential to attract FDI since they have a large domestic market, low inflation, a rising share of trained individuals, a growing entrepreneurial class, and continually developing financial institutions to offer to international investors (Sahoo, 2006).

In the current context, South Asian nation have emerged as a potential investment destination. As a result, evaluating the impact of FDI inflows on the economic performance of these countries has become crucial. In the past two decades, global FDI inflows increased by more than fivefold (USD 341 billion in 1995 to USD 1.76 trillion in 2015). Over time, developing nations' proportion of global FDI inflow has grown, while developed countries' share has decreased (till 2014). In 2000, developed nations accounted for 82.5 percent of the total, while emerging countries accounted for only 17 percent. In 2014, developing nations accounted for around 55% of the total, while developed countries accounted for 41%. Developing and developed countries received 43 percent and 54 percent of global FDI inflows, respectively. In 2015, The average annual growth rate of global FDI inflows was 6.2 percent from 2010 to 2015. FDI inflows grew at a rate of 4.2 percent for developing nations and 12 percent for rich countries during this time. However, since the 1990s, when most South Asian nations began to liberalise, the percentage of FDI inflow from Asian countries has fluctuated between 60 and 70 percent in all emerging countries.

The 'Research Review' section examines the relevant theoretical and empirical literature on the growth impacts of FDI, with a focus on differences in impacts across sectors. The 'Methodology' section discusses the study's methodology as well as the data utilised and their sources. The econometric modelling exercise's empirical results are presented and analysed in the section 'Empirical Results.' The section 'Conclusion' brings the essay to a close while also pointing out some policy implications.

Literature Review

South Asian countries pioneered the liberalisation process by allowing foreign money to flow freely into their economies. As a result, FDI has increased dramatically in recent years in this region, yet the influence of FDI on economic growth is unclear. As a result, scholars and policymakers have begun to pay attention to studies on the impact of foreign direct investment on these economies. Given the uncertainty surrounding the function of FDI, the current study joins the stream of research looking at the influence of FDI and other deciding variables in the instance of South Asian economies.

Many studies (e.g., Griffin, 1970; Singer, 1950) have found that FDI has a detrimental influence on economic growth in underdeveloped nations. According to recent research by Saqib et al. (2013), foreign investment has a negative impact on the economy of Pakistan, but local investment has a positive impact. Over a 35-year span, Herzer (2012) discovered that FDI had a negative influence on developing country development rates.

He came to the conclusion that removing market distortionary policies, reducing natural resource dependency, and improving economic and political stability can safeguard nations from the negative effects of FDI while also promoting FDI-led growth in the long run. Minhaj et al. (2007), on the other hand, determined that FDI inflows boost the economy's socio-economic situation both in the short and long run. Many research (e.g., Agrawal, 2000; Balasubramanyam et al., 1996; Iqbal et al., 2014) have highlighted trade openness as a pre-requisite condition for reaping

good FDI benefits. This is due to Bhagwati's theory that FDI has a stronger influence on GDP in an export-oriented country. Iram and Nishat (2009) investigated the FDI-growth relationship in Pakistan's industrial and service sectors. They discovered that macroeconomic stability and privatisation policies are critical in realising the influence of FDI on economic growth, and that export-oriented policies are also required. Tintin's (2012) study confirmed the positive correlation between FDI and growth, but found that the influence is greater in emerging nations than in developed and least developed countries. He emphasises pro-FDI policies and institutional quality improvement as they are intertwined with growth and development.

Namrata Shrivastava (2019)¹ discovered a strong association between MSIZE, EXP as a percentage of GDP, FOREX and EXTDEBT in a casual factor analysis of FDI inflows in India and that these variables were positively associated. TRADEOPEN, REER, and IIP were determined to be statistically significant. Namrata Shrivastava (2017)² examined the variables impacting FDI inflows in India and discovered that External Debt, FOREX, REER, and Trade Openness are major and significant affecting factors of Foreign Direct Investment Inflows in India.

For the period 1970-2008, Belloumi (2014) examined the link between FDI, trade openness and economic development in Tunisia. To determine the short-run and long-run dynamics among the variables, he used the ARDL bound test and the Granger causality test. The study's findings suggest that FDI and economic growth have a negligible causal relationship. The study's findings contradict the widely held belief that FDI has an inevitable beneficial influence on economic growth. Herzer et al. (2008) used the cointegration approach to examine time series data from 28 nations and contradict the conventional view that FDI promotes economic development. For the majority of nations, the study revealed no effect of FDI on economic growth in the long or short run. The impact of FDI on economic growth varies by country, kind, and destination sector. According to the findings, there is no obvious relationship between the growth impact of FDI and per capita income, education, financial market development, or degree of openness in developing nations.

Research Methodology

The study is based on secondary sources of the statistics. This becomes more essential when the numbers of variables are large; it requires adequate degree of freedom to carry out the traditional statistical tests of significance. Thus, to cater this need of the research a period of 31 years was thoughtfully selected. The data for the purpose of analysis will constitute time series incorporating a period of 1990 to 2020. The present study aims at analysing the long run relationship between Foreign Direct Investment inflows in South Asian Countries. Since the study is based on secondary statistics.

¹ Shrivastava, N. (2019), "[Causal Factor Analysis of Foreign Direct Investment Inflow into India: An Econometric Analysis](#)", VOL-7, ISSUE-35.

² Shrivastava, N. (2017), "Factors Affecting FDI Inflows in India", International Journal of Comprehensive Research in Economics (IJCRE), Bhopal, INDIA, VOLUME-III, Page No—01-08.

The data used in the study are annual data for the period 1990 to 2020 sourced from the various publication of RBI Handbook, DIPP and Stasticstimes.com, Ministry of Finance Govt. of India UNCTADSTAT. various articles, Publications of the World Bank, and various books etc. Tabular form has been used in analysing the collected data. Percentage and ratio are also used in analysing the collected data.

Objectives of the Study:

The specific objectives of the present study are as under:

- To understand the economy of South Asian countries
- To find out the need for FDI to the economic development of South Asian countries
- To present the trend of FDI inflows into South Asian countries
- To outline the possible suggestions for the better inflows of FDI into South Asian countries for economic development

FDI POLICIES IN SOUTH ASIAN COUNTERIES

Evolution of the FDI policy in India: The Foreign Exchange Regulation Act (FERA) was superseded by the Foreign Exchange Management Act (FEMA) between 1991 and 2000, resulting in a dramatic liberalisation of the procedures for foreign investment in India. This shift was reflected in a surge in Foreign Direct Investment of up to 51% in 35 high-priority business sectors, which grew to 111 industries by 1996. On the other side, the Foreign Investment Promotional Board (FIPB) was established to hear matters involving foreign investments. The difference between FEMA and FERA is that FEMA enabled trade practises whereas FERA prohibited abuse of the laws, i.e., FEMA shifted its emphasis from control to management in FERA. During the period 2007-2021, India stayed resilient to the global economic downturn. Due to a lack of funds, the growth pace has slowed slightly. In 2010, the process of rationalisation was accelerated, and all foreign investment legislation were combined into a circular and maintained by the institutions of financial and economic. The Indian government ultimately granted foreign investors permission to establish 100 percent owned subsidiaries in India. Although global economies began to recover from recession between 2011 and 2015, India has had a slow growth rate, which is due to a current account deficit. and outflow of capital. Currency devaluation, rising inflation, deteriorating forex reserves, and exorbitant crude oil/gold import taxes are all contributing factors to the current situation.

However, in 1991, the nation launched a series of policy initiatives to liberalise the FDI environment, including a new economic strategy and a new industrial policy. As a result, India now boasts one of the most attractive foreign direct investment regimes in the area.

Evolution of the FDI Policy in Bangladesh: Bangladesh's FDI regime enjoyed a banner year in FY 2019, with a record amount of net FDI inflows of USD 3.88 billion. However, owing to the omission of investment data from the fourth quarter of 2019, this statistic contradicts UNCTAD's report, suggesting an instance of misrepresentation. According to the Bangladesh Investment Development Authority and Bangladesh Bank, FDI inflows increased to USD 2.58 billion in FY 2019 from USD 2.58 billion in FY 2018. Despite having seen significant economic growth of 8.1 percent previous to the pandemic, Bangladesh has failed to attract FDI as evidenced by the low FDI to GDP ratio of 0.5 percent in 2019. Some of the key causes are infrastructural constraints and a gap in policy implementation. The year-long epidemic has, predictably, delayed global FDI

flows. According to the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development's (UNCTAD) World Investment Report 2020, FDI flows would fall by 40% in 2020. Nonetheless, with the revival of economies, the numbers are likely to be constant in 2021.

Evolution of the FDI Policy in Pakistan: Toward the end of the 1980s, Pakistan began to open up its economy and liberalise its FDI rules. In 1989, a new industrial strategy package was established that recognised the private sector's role and importance, and a number of regulatory measures were implemented to enhance the business climate in general and encourage FDI in particular. The Board of Investment (BOI), which is part of the PM's secretariat, was established to help promote FDI possibilities and provide investment services. BOI is a "one-stop shop" that assists in the development of new businesses. Pakistan has inked bilateral investment promotion and protection agreements with 46 countries to promote international investment. Pakistan's foreign direct investment averaged 158.45 million dollars from 1997 to 2021, with a peak of 1262.90 USD million in June 2008 and a low of -390.90 USD million in October 2018. In September 2021, Pakistan's foreign direct investment grew by 236 million dollars.

Evolution of the FDI Policy in Sri Lanka: FDI in Sri Lanka declined to \$548 million in 2020, from \$793 million in 2019 and \$1.6 billion in 2018. The real estate, mixed-use development projects, ports, and telecommunications industries received the most recent FDI. The tourism sector is a priority area for the government's post-pandemic economic recovery strategy, with roughly two million visitor visits per year (pre-global COVID-19 pandemic) and a range of cultural, wildlife, and outdoor offers. The business process outsourcing industry is also booming, with a lot of American companies involved. Sri Lanka's current account deficit was \$992 million in June 2021, according to the most recent statistics. In June 2021, Sri Lankan Direct Investment Abroad increased by 4.4 million dollars. In June 2021, its Foreign Portfolio Investment declined by 5.3 million dollars. In December 2020, the country's nominal GDP was reported to be 21.8 USD billion.

Evolution of the FDI Policy in Nepal: FDI is critical to the development of rising market trends in the country. It has a strong relationship between foreign investment and the country's economic growth, allowing the poor capital country to construct physical capital, increase productive capacity, improve local labour skills, and generate job opportunities throughout the country. The Fundamental Law Nepal will make numerous efforts to increase FDI in Nepal, including promoting the quality of local products and services, improving human resources, reducing social problems, creating job opportunities, and eliminating unemployment rates, providing equality in terms of race, colour, and creed in competitive advantages for upgrading business, allowing diversification of local markets, increasing business and paying taxes appropriately, and many other efforts to increase foreign direct investment. The service sector accounts for 70.2 percent (Rs. 96.7 billion) of total FDI stock, industry accounts for 29.5 percent (Rs. 40.6 billion), and agricultural accounts for the remaining 0.3 percent (Rs. 395 million).

FIG:1

Source: - Stasticstimes.com

FIG:1 Show 5 Asian countries FDI inflows % of GDP status. In year 2000 FDI Inflows % of GDP found 11.80% and in net years we saw the percentage rate was decline, in year 2006, 2007 and 2007 FDI Inflows % of GDP found increasing rate, apart from next year’s found increase and decrease of FDI Inflows % of GDP.

FIG:2

Source: -World Bank

Growth % of GDP In South Asian Countries

GDP at purchaser's price is that the total of gross value created by all resident producers within the economy plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included within the product's value. it's estimated without accounting for the depreciation of manufactured assets or the depletion and deterioration of natural resources. The figures are in current US dollars. GDP numbers in dollars are translated from domestic currencies employing a single year's worth of official exchange rates. another factor is employed in some countries if the official rate per unit doesn't match the speed effectively applied to actual interchange transactions.

- GDP South Asia in 2020 was \$3,351.52B, decline 6.82% from 2019.
- GDP South Asia in 2019 was \$3,596.91B, increase 4.66% from 2018.
- GDP South Asia in 2018 was \$3,436.88B, increase 2.65% from 2017.
- GDP South Asia in 2017 was \$3,348.22B, increase 14.42% from 2016.

FIG: 3

Source: -World Bank

Per Capita income % of GDP In South Asian Countries

GDP per capita is calculated by dividing gross domestic product by the midyear population. GDP is calculated because the total of the gross value contributed by all resident producers within the economy, plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included within the product value. it's computed without regard for depreciation of manufactured assets or depletion and deterioration of natural resources. The figures are in current US dollars.

- GDP per capita South Asia in 2020 was \$1,805, decline 7.88% from 2019.
- GDP per capita South Asia in 2019 was \$1,959, increase 3.44% from 2018.
- GDP per capita South Asia in 2018 was \$1,894, increase 1.43% from 2017.
- GDP per capita South Asia in 2017 was \$1,868, increase 13.03% from 2016.

FIG: 4

Source: -World Bank

FDI Inflows % of GDP In South Asian Countries

Direct investment equity flows within the reporting economy are cited as foreign direct investment (FDI). it's the whole of equity capital, profits reinvestment, and other capital. Direct investment could be a variety of cross-border investment during which someone from one country has control over or a substantial amount of influence over the management of a corporation in another country. The presence of an on-the-spot investment link is decided by the ownership of 10% or more of the standard shares of stock. The figures are in U.S. dollars at the time of publication.

- FDI inflows South Asia in 2019 was \$56.69B, increase 16.52% from 2018.
- FDI inflows South Asia in 2018 was \$48.66B, increase 5.01% from 2017.
- FDI inflows South Asia in 2017 was \$46.33B, decline 9.03% from 2016.
- FDI inflows South Asia in 2016 was \$50.93B, increase 2.44% from 2015.

FIG: 5

Source: -World Bank

Trade Openness % of GDP In South Asian Countries

The total of commodities and services exported and imported as a percentage of GDP is known as trade.

- Trade openness South Asia in 2020 was 35.24%, decline 3.67% from 2019.
- Trade openness South Asia in 2019 was 38.92%, decline 3.39% from 2018.
- Trade openness South Asia in 2018 was 42.31%, increase 2.89% from 2017.
- Trade openness South Asia in 2017 was 39.42%, increase 0.47% from 2016.

FIG: 6

Source: -World Bank

Labour Force Participation Rate % of GDP In South Asian Countries

The labour force participation rate for persons aged 15 to 24 is that the percentage of the population aged 15 to 24 who are economically active, defined as all those that offer labour for the assembly of products and services within a specific period of time.

- Labour force participation rate South Asia in 2019 was 31.51%, decline 0.43% from 2018.
- Labour force participation rate South Asia in 2018 was 31.94%, decline 0.67% from 2017.

- Labour force participation rate South Asia in 2017 was 32.62%, decline 0.44% from 2016.
- Labour force participation rate South Asia in 2016 was 33.06%, decline 0.75% from 2015.

FIG: 7

Source: -World Bank

Literacy Rate % of GDP In South Asian Countries

The percentage of adults aged 15 and above who can read and write a brief straightforward statement about their daily lives is known as the adult literacy rate.

- Literacy rate South Asia in 2019 was **72.95%**, increase **0.71%** from 2018.
- Literacy rate South Asia in 2018 was **72.24%**, increase **0.55%** from 2017.
- Literacy rate South Asia in 2017 was **71.70%**, increase **0.7%** from 2016.
- Literacy rate South Asia in 2016 was **71.00%**, increase **1.34%** from 2015.

Summary and Conclusion

The Present paper analysed the determinants of FDI inflows in south Asian countries. Paper has discussed the changes in the various determinants of FDI over the period 1990-2020. Tabular analysing, percentage and ratio are also used in analysing the collected data. FDI flows to South Asia increased by 10% to \$57 billion. The rise was driven largely by a 20% increase in investment in India, the largest South Asian FDI recipient, to \$51 billion. Most of the investments in India went to the information and communication technology (ICT) and the construction industries. Flows to Bangladesh fell by 56% to about \$2 billion, reflecting an adjustment from a record-high level in 2018. In Pakistan, FDI recovered, growing 28% to \$2 billion after a 30% fall in 2018. We found that GDP % growth of South Asia in 2019 was \$3,596.91B, increase 4.66% from 2018, GDP per capita South Asia in 2019 was \$1,959, increase 3.44% from 2018, FDI inflows South Asia in 2019 was \$56.69B, increase 16.52% from 2018, Trade openness South Asia in 2018 was 42.31%, increase 2.89% from 2017 and Literacy rate South Asia in 2019 was 72.95%, increase 0.71% from 2018. The multiple regression finding show that FDI and all its possible factors have a long run equilibrium connection beside only one variable. In year 2000 FDI Inflows % of GDP found 11.80% and in net years we saw the percentage rate was decline, in year 2006, 2007 and 2007 FDI Inflows % of GDP found increasing rate, apart from next year's found increase and decrease of FDI Inflows % of GDP. South Asian countries must maintain their growth momentum, set up

measures to better utilise their enormous labour pools, improve infrastructure, and put more open trade policies into place if they are to draw in more FDI.

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